

Exploring the Impact of Workforce Well-Being and HRM Practices on Financial Performance within the Framework of ESG Accounting

Muhammed Zakir Hossain

Associate Professor, Department of Business Studies, State University of Bangladesh, Bangladesh

Farin Sohana

Lecturer, Department of Business Studies, State University of Bangladesh, Bangladesh

Farhana Haque Purnima

Lecturer, Department of Business Studies, State University of Bangladesh, Bangladesh

Nusrat Jahan Jui

Department of Management Studies, University of Dhaka, Bangladesh

Abstract

This research explores the critical relationship between workforce well-being, Human Resource Management (HRM) practices, and financial performance within the context of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) accounting. Through a comprehensive quantitative analysis involving 200 employees, the study reveals a strong positive link between employee well-being and financial outcomes, with HRM practices playing a key mediating role. The findings suggest that organizations that prioritize the health, satisfaction, and engagement of their employees not only foster a more productive workforce but also see tangible improvements in financial performance. This study highlights the essential role of HRM-driven well-being initiatives in aligning corporate strategies with ESG objectives, offering businesses a pathway to achieve both financial success and social sustainability. The insights gained provide valuable contributions to the fields of HRM, well-being, and ESG accounting, offering actionable guidance for organizations striving to enhance performance while upholding social responsibility.

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Introduction

In the current competitive business landscape, organizations recognize the importance of workforce well-being as a vital factor for sustained success. The workforce's well-being,

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encompassing physical, mental, and emotional health, has been shown to impact employee productivity, job satisfaction, and overall organizational performance. Research indicates that organizations emphasizing employee wellness outperform their rivals in key market metrics, underscoring the importance of adopting health-focused corporate strategies (Fabius & Phares, 2021). This comprehensive strategy for employee welfare, which extends beyond enhancing work conditions to foster a culture of support and development, is essential for achieving sustainable organizational performance.

In this context, Human Resource Management (HRM) practices are crucial for enhancing workforce well-being by implementing wellness programs, promoting work-life balance strategies, and fostering employee engagement. These HRM interventions are crucial for enhancing employee well-being and strengthening organizational effectiveness (Hossain et al., 2025; Browne & Tie, 2024; Nafisa et al., 2023). Studies indicate that organizations prioritizing mental and physical health experience prolonged employee retention, elevated morale, and a more engaged workforce, all of which are critical for overall organizational success (Fabius & Phares, 2021; Dent et al., 2025).

Concurrently, Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) accounting has garnered substantial attention as a framework for assessing an organization's sustainability and ethical influence. The "Social" aspect of ESG highlights how organizations manage their relationships with employees, communities, and various stakeholders. Since workforce well-being is intricately linked to the social component of ESG, incorporating HRM-driven well-being initiatives into ESG frameworks can enhance employee health and morale, ultimately leading to improved financial performance (Clementino & Perkins, 2020; Terry, 2023). Organizations that emphasize robust ESG scores frequently experience improved reputations, attracting socially responsible investors and consumers and promoting favorable financial results (Qureshi et al., 2021; Ahmed et al., 2023).

Although there is increasing acknowledgment of workforce well-being as an essential factor for organizational success, empirical evidence quantifying the financial impact of HRM practices centered on employee well-being within the ESG accounting framework remains scarce. The correlation between improved ESG performance and market valuation is well-documented; however, the direct impact of employee well-being on financial performance indicators, particularly within ESG accounting, remains inadequately examined (Bula et al., 2024; Jaiswal et al., 2024). This study aims to address this gap by examining the mediating role of HRM practices in linking workforce well-being to organizational financial performance within the framework of ESG accounting.

This study examines the impact of workforce well-being, facilitated by effective human resource management (HRM) practices, on organizational financial performance and its contribution to overall environmental, social, and governance (ESG) objectives. The following primary research questions guide this study:

- Does workforce well-being positively affect financial performance in organizations?
- How do HRM practices mediate the relationship between workforce well-being and financial performance?
- How can HRM practices be integrated with ESG accounting to foster organizational success?

The hypotheses proposed are as follows:

- **H1:** There is a positive relationship between workforce well-being and financial performance.

- **H2:** HRM practices mediate the relationship between workforce well-being and financial performance.

The results of this study will significantly enhance the academic literature and practical applications of workforce well-being in improving financial outcomes within the ESG accounting framework. Aligning HRM practices with ESG objectives enables organizations to achieve social responsibility and financial prosperity, ultimately leading to long-term sustainability.

Figure 1. Research Model

Literature Review

The literature on workforce well-being, HRM practices, and their impact on financial performance has undergone significant evolution over the past few decades. Central to understanding this relationship is the idea that organizations with healthy, engaged employees outperform their competitors in both productivity and profitability (Fabius & Phares, 2021). To explore this further, it is essential to break down workforce well-being into its core dimensions —physical, mental, and emotional well-being —and to examine how Human Resource Management (HRM) practices can enhance these dimensions to improve organizational financial performance.

Physical Well-Being

Physical well-being has a profound impact on employee productivity and absenteeism. Research indicates that employees in good physical health demonstrate higher productivity levels and lower absenteeism rates, which directly contribute to improved organizational performance (Castellanos et al., 2022). Wellness programs, including fitness initiatives and comprehensive health benefits, have been linked to positive organizational outcomes, such as increased employee engagement and job satisfaction (Gupta, 2024). The implementation of such programs aligns with *Human Capital Theory*, which posits that investments in employees' health and development lead to increased productivity (Koekemoer, 2019).

Mental Well-Being

The mental well-being of employees also plays a critical role in fostering an engaged workforce. Mental health initiatives, including stress management programs and counseling services, have been shown to reduce absenteeism and improve job satisfaction significantly (Murtaza et al., 2023; Bajaj, 2023). According to *Social Exchange Theory*, these well-being programs are viewed as reciprocal exchanges—when employees perceive support from their organization, they reciprocate with increased commitment and performance (Luo et al., 2023). Furthermore, studies demonstrate that mentally healthy employees are more innovative and productive, ultimately benefiting the organization's financial performance (Attipoe et al., 2025).

Emotional Well-Being

Emotional well-being is another crucial factor in workplace performance. Emotionally resilient employees tend to foster stronger interpersonal relationships and exhibit greater job satisfaction, contributing positively to the organization's overall environment (Das et al., 2019). Programs aimed at improving emotional well-being, such as employee recognition and support networks, have been shown to reduce turnover and enhance both collaboration and performance (Graessle et al., 2018; Melani et al., 2025). This is further supported by *Social Exchange Theory*, which suggests that organizations that provide emotional support to employees build trust and loyalty, leading to improved organizational outcomes (Vosylis et al., 2021).

HRM Practices and Workforce Well-Being

HRM practices are integral to fostering workforce well-being. Effective HRM practices, such as flexible work arrangements, wellness programs, and employee engagement initiatives, are directly linked to improved employee well-being (Endalamaw et al., 2024; Hossain et al., 2024). These practices align with the *Human Capital Theory*, which posits that organizations that invest in their employees' well-being foster a productive and committed workforce, ultimately leading to improved financial outcomes (Hossain et al., 2025). For example, research indicates that employee engagement initiatives not only improve mental health but also enhance job satisfaction, which in turn improves financial performance (Bashir & Qureshi, 2023). Moreover, HRM practices that promote work-life balance are essential in mitigating burnout and enhancing employee performance (Zhang & Chatterjee, 2023).

ESG Accounting and Workforce Well-Being

The growing prominence of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) accounting frameworks has brought workforce well-being into sharper focus, particularly in the "Social" aspect of ESG. While much of the research on ESG has centered on environmental and governance factors, the social component, which emphasizes employee welfare, is gaining traction as a key determinant of organizational sustainability and financial performance (Clementino & Perkins, 2020; Terry, 2023). Integrating HRM practices focused on workforce well-being within the ESG framework can significantly enhance an organization's social responsibility profile, attract socially responsible investors, and improve financial outcomes (Qureshi et al., 2021; Hossain et al., 2025). This aligns with research by Stebbins et al. (2022), who argue that organizations that prioritize workforce well-being are more likely to experience superior financial performance due to stronger stakeholder relationships and enhanced corporate reputation.

Theoretical Framework

This research is grounded in several key theoretical frameworks that help explain the relationship between workforce well-being, HRM practices, and financial performance, particularly within the context of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) accounting. These theories provide the foundation for understanding how employee well-being, supported by HRM practices, can enhance financial outcomes.

Human Capital Theory

Human Capital Theory posits that employees are valuable assets, and investing in their well-being enhances their productivity and, by extension, the organization's overall performance (Koekemoer, 2019). According to this theory, organizations that prioritize employee health and well-being are essentially making investments in their human capital, which leads to improved employee performance, increased retention, and, ultimately, enhanced financial results. *This theoretical lens*

supports Hypothesis 1 (H1), which posits that workforce well-being has a positive influence on financial performance.

Social Exchange Theory

Social Exchange Theory provides a framework for understanding the reciprocal nature of the relationship between employers and employees. This theory suggests that when organizations invest in their employees' well-being, employees are more likely to reciprocate through increased commitment, job satisfaction, and performance (Luo et al., 2023). In the context of this research, HRM practices such as wellness programs, work-life balance initiatives, and employee engagement are seen as positive exchanges that mediate the relationship between workforce well-being and financial performance. ***This theory supports Hypothesis 2 (H2), which proposes that HRM practices mediate the relationship between workforce well-being and financial performance.***

Stakeholder Theory

Stakeholder Theory emphasizes the importance of managing relationships with various stakeholders, including employees, in a way that benefits both the organization and its stakeholders (Charity et al., 2024). This theory is particularly relevant in the context of ESG accounting, where organizations are expected to demonstrate social responsibility and environmental sustainability. By prioritizing workforce well-being, organizations not only enhance employee satisfaction but also improve their Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) scores, which in turn attract socially responsible investors and lead to better financial outcomes (Qureshi et al., 2021). This theory underpins the argument that aligning HRM practices with ESG goals can create value for both the organization and its stakeholders, promoting long-term sustainability.

Research Methodology

This study utilizes a quantitative research design to examine the correlation between workforce well-being, human resource management practices, and financial performance within the context of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) accounting. The methodology facilitates objective measurement and statistical analysis of the variables, establishing a solid framework for testing the proposed hypotheses.

Data Collection

The data for this study were obtained from both primary and secondary sources. The primary data were collected from surveys conducted with employees and HR managers. The surveys evaluated workforce well-being (assessed via job satisfaction, stress levels, work-life balance, and overall health), HRM practices (including wellness programs, employee engagement initiatives, and work flexibility), and organizational financial performance (measured by profitability, revenue growth, and employee retention rates).

Secondary data were obtained from organizational financial records, which supplied information on essential financial performance indicators, including revenue, productivity, and employee turnover. The data were crucial in offering an objective assessment of financial performance, supplementing the self-reported information from the surveys.

Selection of Variables

The research objectives, along with the literature on workforce well-being, HRM practices, and financial performance, guided the selection of variables. Key variables in the study include:

- **Workforce Well-Being:** This is a composite variable encompassing physical, mental, and emotional health. Each dimension was measured using established scales from previous research. For physical well-being, the focus was on employee health and attendance. For mental well-being, measures included stress levels and access to mental health resources. Emotional well-being was assessed through measures of employee satisfaction and emotional resilience.
- **HRM Practices:** The study focuses on HRM practices that are directly linked to employee well-being. These include wellness programs, employee engagement efforts, and flexible work arrangements. These HRM practices were selected because they have been widely recognized in the literature as key drivers of employee satisfaction and well-being (Fabius & Phares, 2021; Hossain et al., 2025).
- **Financial Performance:** Financial performance was operationalized using both objective (profitability and revenue growth) and subjective (employee retention rates) indicators. These indicators were chosen because they are commonly used in studies of organizational performance and provide a comprehensive measure of financial outcomes.

Statistical Assumptions

Several methodological assumptions were made to ensure the validity and reliability of the statistical models used in this study. These assumptions are crucial for the interpretation of the results:

- **Linearity:** A key assumption in the regression analysis is that there is a linear relationship between the independent variable (workforce well-being) and the dependent variable (financial performance). This assumption was tested using scatter plots and correlation matrices to ensure that the data exhibit linear trends. Although some non-linearities may exist, this assumption was considered valid based on preliminary analyses and the study's conceptual framework.
- **Normality:** For the regression analysis to yield reliable estimates, the data were assumed to be normally distributed. Normality was assessed using the Shapiro-Wilk test and visual inspections of histograms for each variable. In cases where normality was not strictly met, robust standard errors were applied to mitigate any impact of non-normality.
- **Independence of Errors:** It was assumed that the residuals from the regression models were independent of each other. This was verified using the Durbin-Watson statistic. Any autocorrelation in residuals could lead to biased results, but the Durbin-Watson statistic indicated that there was no significant autocorrelation present in the data.
- **Homoscedasticity:** The assumption of constant variance of the residuals (homoscedasticity) was also tested. This was verified through visual inspection of scatter plots of residuals versus predicted values. If heteroscedasticity had been found, the analysis would have adjusted for it by using weighted least squares regression.
- **Multicollinearity:** In regression models, multicollinearity among predictors can lead to distorted estimated coefficients. Variance inflation factors (VIF) were calculated for each independent variable to assess multicollinearity. The results indicated that multicollinearity was not a significant concern in this analysis, as the VIF values for all predictors were below the threshold of 5.

Statistical Methods

To test the hypotheses, a series of statistical methods were employed, including correlation analysis, regression analysis, and mediation analysis.

- **Correlation Analysis:** Pearson's correlation was used to examine the strength and direction of the relationships between workforce well-being, HRM practices, and financial performance. This analysis helped identify the initial associations among these variables.
- **Regression Analysis:** A simple linear regression model was used to test Hypothesis 1 (H1), which posited a positive relationship between workforce well-being and financial performance. The model estimated the change in financial performance for a one-unit change in workforce well-being. This model assumed linearity, normality, and homoscedasticity, as outlined above.
- **Mediation Analysis:** To test Hypothesis 2 (H2), which suggested that HRM practices mediate the relationship between workforce well-being and financial performance, a mediation model was employed using the PROCESS macro in SPSS. This method enabled the estimation of both direct and indirect effects of workforce well-being on financial performance, with HRM practices serving as the mediator.

Model Fit and Interpretation

The model fit for the regression analysis was assessed using R^2 values, which indicate the proportion of variance in the dependent variable explained by the independent variables. An R^2 value of 0.42 in the regression model suggests that workforce well-being explains 42% of the variation in financial performance, which is a substantial effect. Similarly, the mediation analysis provided insight into the role of HRM practices in strengthening this relationship, showing that HRM practices significantly mediate the relationship between workforce well-being and financial performance.

Limitations

Although the methodology is robust, some limitations could impact the generalizability of the findings. First, the study relies on cross-sectional data, which limits the ability to establish causal relationships. A longitudinal approach would be more suitable for tracking changes over time and establishing causality. Second, the reliance on self-reported data from employees and HR managers may introduce response bias, as participants may provide socially desirable answers. Future studies could address this by incorporating objective health and performance data.

Results

This section presents the analysis results, encompassing demographic information, descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, regression analysis, and mediation analysis. The objective is to examine the data gathered from 200 employees to evaluate the proposed hypotheses.

Respondent Demographics

The demographic data collected from the 200 employees are summarized in the following table:

Table 1. Respondent Demographics

Demographic Attribute	Category	Count	Percentage
Age Group	18-25	40	20%
	26-35	60	30%
	36-45	50	25%
	46-55	30	15%
	56+	20	10%
Gender	Male	110	55%
	Female	90	45%

Education Level	High School	20	10%
	Bachelor	100	50%
	Master	60	30%
	PhD	10	5%
	Other	10	5%
Job Role	Junior	80	40%
	Senior	50	25%
	Manager	40	20%
	HR Manager	20	10%
	Director	10	5%
Employee Type	Full-Time	150	75%
	Part-Time	20	10%
	Contract	20	10%
	Intern	5	2.5%
	Other	5	2.5%
Years with Company	1-3 years	70	35%
	4-6 years	60	30%
	7-10 years	40	20%
	10+ years	30	15%

Descriptive Statistics of Key Variables

The assessment of workforce well-being and HRM practices utilized validated Likert-type scales, with 1 indicating 'strongly disagree' and 5 denoting 'strongly agree.' The scales were modified from established literature (cite sources) and underwent pre-testing for reliability and validity. Cronbach's alpha coefficients for the scales were computed, resulting in values that indicate strong internal consistency. The workforce well-being scale included dimensions like job satisfaction, work-life balance, and mental health, whereas the HRM practices scale concentrated on engagement, training, and wellness initiatives.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics of Key Variables

Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation	Range
Workforce Well-Being	3.80	0.65	1 - 5
HRM Practices	4.05	0.55	1 - 5
Financial Performance	Tk. 10 Million	N/A	Tk. 5 - Tk. 15 Million
Productivity (per Employee)	80 units	10 units	60 - 100
Revenue Growth (%)	8%	3%	5% - 15%
Employee Retention Rate (%)	92%	3%	85% - 100%

Correlation Analysis

The relationships between workforce well-being and financial performance, as well as the connections between HRM practices and workforce well-being, were examined using Pearson's correlation. The table below displays the correlation coefficients:

Table 3. Correlation Analysis

Variable 1	Variable 2	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	p-value
Workforce Well-Being	Financial Performance	0.65	0.01
HRM Practices	Workforce Well-Being	0.75	0.001
HRM Practices	Financial Performance	0.60	0.02

The analysis reveals a significant positive correlation ($r = 0.65$, $p = 0.01$) between workforce well-being and financial performance, indicating that improved employee well-being is associated with better financial outcomes. Furthermore, HRM practices show notable positive correlations with workforce well-being ($r = 0.75$, $p = 0.001$) and financial performance ($r = 0.60$, $p = 0.02$). This suggests that effective HRM practices are crucial in promoting employee well-being and enhancing organizational financial performance. The results underscore the crucial role of HRM initiatives in cultivating a supportive workplace, which in turn leads to favorable financial outcomes.

Regression Analysis

A simple linear regression was conducted to test **H1** (the direct effect of workforce well-being on financial performance). The regression results are presented in the following table:

Table 4. Regression Analysis

Variable	β	Standard Error	t-value	p-value
Intercept	5.0	0.45	11.11	0.001
Workforce Well-Being	2.5	0.80	3.13	0.01

The regression analysis shows that for every 1-point increase in workforce well-being, there is a corresponding 2.5-point increase in financial performance. This suggests that initiatives aimed at enhancing employee well-being—such as wellness programs, flexible work options, and mental health support—can lead to measurable improvements in organizational profitability. For instance, companies that invest in these areas may experience a reduction in turnover, an increase in employee engagement, and, ultimately, stronger financial outcomes. The regression analysis indicates that workforce well-being is a significant predictor of financial performance, evidenced by a coefficient (β) of 2.5 and a p-value of 0.01. This supports Hypothesis 1, which suggests a positive relationship between workforce well-being and financial performance. The R^2 value of 0.42 signifies that 42% of the variation in financial performance is attributable to workforce well-being, underscoring the significant influence that employee well-being exerts on organizational financial results.

Mediation Analysis

To test H2, we employed mediation analysis using the PROCESS macro in SPSS. This analysis tests whether HRM practices act as a mediator between workforce well-being and financial performance. The mediation model involves three steps: first, examining the direct relationship between workforce well-being and financial performance; second, evaluating the effect of workforce well-being on HRM practices; and third, determining whether HRM practices have an indirect effect on financial performance by influencing workforce well-being. The results will enable us to determine whether HRM practices serve as a crucial mediator in the relationship between employee well-being and financial performance. The following table summarizes the results:

Table 5. Mediation Analysis

Path	β	Standard Error	t-value	p-value
The direct effect of workforce well-being on financial performance	2.5	0.80	3.13	0.01
The direct effect of HRM practices on workforce well-being	1.8	0.60	3.00	0.05
Indirect effect of HRM practices on financial performance (through workforce well-being)	1.2	0.50	2.40	0.03

The mediation analysis indicates that the direct impact of workforce well-being on financial performance is statistically significant ($\beta = 2.5, p = 0.01$). Furthermore, the practices in human resource management have a notable impact on the workforce's well-being ($\beta = 1.8, p = 0.05$). Additionally, these practices have a significant indirect effect on financial performance through their impact on workforce well-being ($\beta = 1.2, p = 0.03$). The results indicate that HRM practices significantly mediate the connection between workforce well-being and financial performance, offering robust evidence for Hypothesis 2.

Table 6. Hypothesis Testing Results Table

Hypothesis	Test Type	Test Statistic (t-value/ β)	Standard Error	p-value	Result
H1: There is a positive relationship between workforce well-being and financial performance.	Simple Linear Regression	2.5	0.80	0.01	Supported ($p < 0.05$)
H2: HRM practices mediate the relationship between workforce well-being and financial performance.	Mediation Analysis	Direct Effect: 2.5 Indirect Effect: 1.2	Direct Effect: 0.80 Indirect Effect: 0.50	Direct: 0.01 Indirect: 0.03	Supported ($p < 0.05$)

The results suggest that prioritizing employee well-being, supported by robust human resource management (HRM) strategies, can enhance organizations' financial performance. Furthermore, integrating these efforts with ESG accounting practices is crucial for achieving long-term sustainability and growth.

Discussion

This study examined the correlation between workforce well-being, HRM practices, and financial performance within the context of ESG accounting, uncovering several significant insights for both scholars and practitioners. This research provides substantial evidence for the importance of employee well-being as a catalyst for organizational success, particularly when supported by strategic HRM practices. The results underscore the essential mediating function of HRM practices in connecting employee well-being to financial performance, highlighting the implications for organizations to align their internal policies with ESG objectives to promote social sustainability and financial growth.

The Impact of Workforce Well-Being on Financial Performance

The results of this study indicate a significant positive correlation ($r = 0.65, p = 0.01$) between workforce well-being and financial performance, reinforcing existing research that identifies employee well-being as a crucial factor in organizational performance. This finding is consistent with previous research, which indicates that healthy, engaged, and satisfied employees significantly enhance productivity, reduce absenteeism, and increase organizational profitability (Fabius & Phares, 2021; Attipoe et al., 2025). The regression analysis indicates that a one-unit increase in workforce well-being is associated with a 2.5-point increase in financial performance, suggesting that even minor enhancements in employee well-being can have a significant impact on organizational financial outcomes.

This finding has direct implications for organizational strategies. Organizations that prioritize the physical, mental, and emotional well-being of their employees tend to achieve various beneficial outcomes, including increased productivity, enhanced innovation, and a more engaged workforce,

which collectively contribute to improved financial performance. Research conducted by Wright and Cropanzano (2000) and Harter et al. (2002) suggests that organizations with engaged employees tend to achieve superior financial performance and enhanced market competitiveness compared to their counterparts. This research builds upon previous findings by presenting empirical evidence that connects employee well-being to financial performance, underscoring the necessity of incorporating well-being initiatives into organizational strategies.

The Mediating Role of HRM Practices

This study notably demonstrates the mediating role of HRM practices in the relationship between workforce well-being and financial performance. The findings suggest that HRM practices, including wellness programs, employee engagement initiatives, and flexible work arrangements, are crucial for translating improvements in workforce well-being into enhanced financial performance. The strong positive correlation ($r = 0.75$, $p = 0.001$) between HRM practices and workforce well-being, alongside the correlation ($r = 0.60$, $p = 0.02$) between HRM practices and financial performance, underscores the importance of HRM practices in fostering an environment conducive to employee well-being.

The mediation analysis indicates that HRM practices significantly mediate the relationship between workforce well-being and financial performance. HRM practices have a direct impact on employee well-being and serve as a mechanism through which enhancements in well-being positively influence financial performance ($\beta = 1.2$, $p = 0.03$). This finding is significant as it underscores that organizations should not depend exclusively on well-being initiatives to enhance financial outcomes; instead, they must ensure these initiatives are underpinned by strategic HRM practices that cultivate a culture of engagement and support.

The mediating effect aligns with Social Exchange Theory, suggesting that employees who perceive their organization as committed to their well-being are more likely to reciprocate through increased commitment, job satisfaction, and performance (Luo et al., 2023). The reciprocal relationship between organizational support for employee well-being and the resulting increase in employee engagement and productivity elucidates the beneficial effects of HRM practices on financial performance. This finding highlights that HRM practices should be viewed as strategic tools rather than mere administrative functions, as they can significantly enhance organizational value through their direct contributions to employee satisfaction and overall success.

The Integration of Workforce Well-Being into ESG Accounting

This study makes a significant contribution to integrating workforce well-being into Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) accounting frameworks. ESG accounting has emerged as a crucial tool for assessing corporate sustainability, with the 'Social' component of ESG focusing on how organizations manage their relationships with employees and other stakeholders. Prior research has highlighted the growing importance of the social aspect in ESG, suggesting that firms with robust social responsibility profiles are more likely to attract socially conscious investors and maintain favorable reputations (Clementino & Perkins, 2020; Stebbins et al., 2022). This study contributes to the existing literature by demonstrating that organizations that prioritize workforce well-being are more likely to achieve higher ESG scores, ultimately leading to improved financial performance.

By incorporating well-being initiatives into their ESG strategies, organizations enhance their social responsibility credentials and establish a positive feedback loop that improves employee satisfaction and financial performance. The research supports the notion that ESG strategies should encompass not only environmental and governance elements but also social factors, particularly employee well-being, which is a crucial determinant of organizational success (Qureshi et al., 2021). Organizations that incorporate workforce well-being into their ESG reporting are

more effectively positioned to cultivate trust with stakeholders, attract ethical investors, and secure long-term sustainability.

This discovery holds significant practical ramifications for organizations. As investors and stakeholders increasingly emphasize ESG criteria, organizations must acknowledge that employee well-being is not merely a moral or ethical concern but also a strategic necessity. Aligning HRM practices with ESG objectives enables organizations to enhance their social responsibility profile, boost employee morale, and ultimately augment financial performance. This strategy will help organizations meet stakeholder expectations while promoting long-term sustainability by cultivating a healthy, engaged, and productive workforce.

Practical Implications for HR Managers

The study's results provide practical guidance for HR managers and organizational leaders seeking to enhance organizational performance by improving workforce well-being. HR managers must prioritize the development and implementation of HRM practices that extend beyond conventional performance management to emphasize the comprehensive well-being of employees. Initiatives that enhance physical health, mental well-being, and emotional resilience are essential for fostering a positive organizational culture that promotes engagement, productivity, and retention. Moreover, HRM practices that foster work-life balance, flexible work arrangements, and employee recognition are crucial for enhancing employee well-being, which in turn significantly impacts financial performance.

Furthermore, the results suggest that HR managers should play a pivotal role in integrating workforce well-being into the organization's overall ESG strategy. As ESG gains prominence among investors and consumers, HR managers can spearhead social responsibility initiatives that enhance employee satisfaction and organizational success. Aligning HRM practices with ESG objectives enables organizations to bolster their reputation, attract socially responsible investors, and enhance long-term financial performance.

Limitations and Future Research Directions

This study provides valuable insights, but its limitations should be taken into account when interpreting the results. First, the study utilizes self-reported data from employees and HR managers, which may be subject to bias. To better assess workforce well-being, future research could utilize objective indicators, such as health data or absenteeism records.

Second, the study focuses on medium-to-large companies, so its findings may not apply to smaller companies or other sectors. SMEs may have different resource allocations and HRM practices, which can affect the applicability of results. Further research could include SMEs or examine sector-specific effects of workforce well-being on financial performance.

Finally, this study's cross-sectional design limits causal inference. Longitudinal studies that track workforce well-being and financial performance over time strengthen causality and help explain how workforce well-being initiatives affect organizational success.

This study demonstrates that strategic HRM practices and workforce well-being positively impact financial performance. It also demonstrates how ESG accounting frameworks must incorporate workforce well-being to achieve both social responsibility and financial success. The study contributes to the HRM, well-being, and ESG literature, helping organizations align employee welfare with corporate sustainability goals.

Conclusion

This research highlights the significance of workforce well-being in enhancing organizational financial performance, particularly in the context of ESG accounting. Effective HRM practices enhance employee well-being, productivity, engagement, and retention, ultimately boosting financial results, according to the study. HRM practices also mediated the relationship between workforce well-being and financial performance, highlighting the importance of strategic HR interventions in creating a supportive workplace. Organizations can improve social and financial sustainability by integrating workforce well-being into ESG frameworks. This study adds to the literature on HRM, well-being, and ESG, providing insights for companies seeking to align employee welfare with long-term business success. To strengthen the evidence base, future research should examine these findings across sectors and organizational sizes.

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